

Bleeding evaluation in patients with liver cirrhosis due to therapeutic approach: a statistical overview

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Abstract

In patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis, the presence of acute hemorrhage is a common clinical finding. The different types of bleeding that may be observed include variceal and non-variceal gastrointestinal bleeding and systemic bleeding due to abnormalities in overall coagulation status. This retrospective study included 438 patients with liver cirrhosis who were selected from the endoscopy records. Of all admitted patients, 323 had a variceal source of bleeding. The remaining 115 patients had non-variceal bleeding. The findings show that the most frequent etiology was variceal bleeding. Peptic ulcer (gastric and duodenal ulcer) was dominant (60%) in the etiology of non-variceal upper gastrointestinal bleeding. The significant rate of all acute GI hemorrhage in cirrhosis was variceal, but a considerable proportion had non-variceal causes. Our study showed that in about 26.3% of the cirrhotic patients with upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage, the bleeding occurred from non-variceal sources, of which the most frequent one was ulcer. These results show that therapy should be approached after clinical evaluation and upper gastrointestinal endoscopy.

Keywords

duodenal ulcer, gastrointestinal bleeding therapy, liver cirrhosis, non-variceal bleeding, peptic ulcer disease, portal hypertension, stomach ulcer, variceal bleeding

Introduction

In patients with decompensated liver cirrhosis, the presence of acute hemorrhage is a common clinical finding. The reported prevalence is 100–170:100,000 population. Mortality due to upper gastrointestinal bleeding has remained unchanged for many years, in spite of modern methods of diagnosis and treatment. It is about 10% (Vaz et al. 2021; Shalaby et al. 2024).

The liver is an organ with many functions, the most significant for the current context being that it serves as a reservoir for blood (received via the portal vein) and has a synthetic function—producing a range of proteins involved in hematopoiesis, hemostasis, and fibrinolysis (thrombopoietin, prothrombin, coagulation factors, anti-thrombin) (Romcea et al. 2013; Islam et al. 2022).

The different types of bleeding that may be observed in a patient with liver cirrhosis include variceal and non-variceal gastrointestinal bleeding and systemic bleeding due to abnormalities in overall coagulation status (Elwakil et al. 2011; Gralnek et al. 2022).

A patient with acute bleeding from a variceal source presents predominantly with hematemesis—the vomited blood is dark venous in character and appears in large volume during active bleeding (Elwakil et al. 2011). The presence of dark hematin material (“coffee grounds”) more often indicates gastrointestinal bleeding of non-variceal origin and suggests contact between blood and hydrochloric acid in the stomach (Svoboda et al. 2010; Elwakil et al. 2011). Melena is the passage of black, shiny stools. It may indicate bleeding of more than 100–200 mL or delayed peristalsis with a longer duration of bleeding. It appears as early as 8–10 hours after onset and may persist up to 5 days after cessation (Svoboda et al. 2010). Hematochezia is more common in lower GI bleeding but may also appear in massive upper GI bleeding (Romcea et al. 2013).

Systemic signs of acute blood loss include dizziness, weakness, and lightheadedness. Objective findings include pale skin, cold extremities, and tachycardia accompanied by hypotension. The shock index (pulse/systolic pressure) > 1 must be monitored, as this may indicate severe blood loss and development of hypovolemic shock (Palmer et al. 2002). A significant laboratory drop in hemoglobin is recorded at least 24 hours after bleeding begins. Considering the control group, all additional characteristics of a patient with decompensated liver cirrhosis are taken into account in the clinical picture (Romcea et al. 2013).

Materials and methods

This retrospective study was conducted in the period 2023–2025 at the University Emergency Hospital Pirogov, Sofia, Bulgaria. It included 438 patients with liver cirrhosis who were selected from the endoscopy records.

Over 3 years, 438 patients with liver cirrhosis and evidence of gastrointestinal bleeding were observed. All patients with acute GI bleeding were hospitalized during the same time frame. The patients were men and women between the ages of 34 and 80 years, admitted to the multi-profile emergency department with complaints of acute GI bleeding and with objective findings on admission indicating signs of liver cirrhosis.

Each patient underwent paraclinical testing: complete blood count, biochemistry, and coagulation. An upper gastrointestinal endoscopy was performed on all patients on admission, and an ultrasound examination was conducted, which identified or confirmed an already known hepatic pathology.

The results of the study were processed using the PSPP program. The quantitative data were expressed as medians; descriptive statistics and graphical visualization were used.

Results

The average age of the patients was 57.99 ± 10.72 years, the youngest and the oldest being 34 years and 80 years, respectively. Analysis of the results shows that 315 (71.9%) of all patients were men and 123 (28.1%) were women.

According to the type of bleeding, 323 (73.7%) of all admitted patients had a variceal source of bleeding. Among the remaining 115 patients with non-variceal bleeding, the etiology was distributed as follows: 11.6% (51 patients) had a duodenal ulcer, and 4.1% (18 patients) had a gastric ulcer. The remaining 6.8% (30 patients) included other causes such as erosive gastritis/duodenitis and Mallory–Weiss syndrome. In addition, patients whose bleeding originated from recurrent oral cavity hemorrhages secondary to coagulopathy accounted for 3.7% (16 patients). Results are shown in Fig. 1.

When performing an upper GI endoscopy, variceal blood vessels should be classified according to established endoscopic classifications. The Sarin classification of esophageal varices includes four grades: Grade I—small, straight varices that collapse easily with air insufflation; Grade II—enlarged, tortuous vessels occupying less than one-third of the lumen; Grade III—large, confluent

Figure 1. Pie chart showing distribution of variceal and non-variceal bleeding causes.

varices occupying 33–66% of the lumen, non-collapsible; and Grade IV—varices with the same characteristics as Grade III, but occupying more than two-thirds of the lumen, often with “red cherry spots” (Vaz K et al.).

Gastric varices account for 15–20% of all variceal bleeding, as they lie deeper within the submucosal layer of the gastric wall. Bleeding may occur at lower portal pressures compared with esophageal varices. A considerable number of gastric varices remain undiagnosed during routine endoscopy due to difficulty visualizing vessels hidden within gastric folds.

The Sarin and Kumar classification of gastroesophageal varices is as follows: GOV1—gastroesophageal varices along the lesser curvature of the stomach (approximately 75% of bleeding sources); GOV2—varices extending toward the fundus; IGV1—isolated fundal varices; IGV2—isolated gastric varices located elsewhere in the stomach (< 5%) (Vaz et al. 2021; Shalaby S et al. 2024).

Bleeding cases that were non-variceal were distributed as follows: duodenal ulcer 44.3%, stomach ulcer 15.7%, other non-variceal causes 26.1%, and oral bleeding due to coagulopathy 13.9%. The shares are presented in Fig. 2.

A significant proportion of patients were admitted late in the evening or overnight, which may have several explanations. Studies indicate a physiological increase in portal pressure at night or circadian-related changes in peripheral vascular resistance. In addition, much of the liver cirrhosis in our region is alcohol-related, and alcohol intake generally increases in the evening. Another scenario is that bleeding may start earlier in the day, but melena, being a common symptom, requires about 8–10 hours to transit through the GI tract. Patients often notice this symptom late at night or early in the morning, which is when they seek medical attention (Mann et al. 1999).

Discussion

The results of our study show that, out of the 438 studied patients, the most frequent etiology was variceal bleeding, the results being similar to and in keeping with those reported in the literature (Kim et al. 2012; Gralnek et al. 2022; Islam et al. 2022). Peptic ulcer (gastric and duodenal ulcer) is dominant (60%) in the etiology of non-variceal

Figure 2. Pie chart illustrating the distribution of non-variceal bleeding sources.

upper gastrointestinal bleeding. The most common cause of acute non-variceal bleeding in patients with liver cirrhosis is peptic ulcer disease. The risk factors include mucosal congestion and ischemia due to portal hypertension. Impaired synthesis of clotting factors makes it harder to achieve spontaneous hemostasis.

Given the significant number of non-variceal upper gastrointestinal hemorrhages in cirrhotic patients, prevention of upper gastrointestinal bleeding in these patients becomes of extreme importance, including avoidance of NSAIDs, treatment with proton pump inhibitors in patients with a known ulcer or in those who have ulcer symptoms, and complete endoscopic exploration of patients with liver cirrhosis. A significant rate of all acute GI hemorrhages in cirrhosis is variceal, but the non-variceal rate is also sufficiently high.

The liver synthesizes most coagulation and anticoagulation factors. Therefore, its impairment leads to complex hemostatic changes that complicate any type of bleeding. The most common are GI bleeds, but hemorrhage can occur anywhere vascular integrity is compromised. This includes bleeding around the skin and subcutaneous tissue: petechiae, hematomas with minimal trauma, spontaneous subcutaneous bleeding; mucosal hemorrhages: frequent epistaxis, bleeding from the oral cavity; urogenital bleeding; hematuria, menorrhagia (Hearnshaw et al. 2011; Islam et al. 2022).

Disturbances in primary hemostasis include thrombocytopenia caused by splenomegaly, decreased thrombopoietin production, and bone marrow function suppression (due to alcohol abuse or viral liver disease). Platelet dysfunction is present but is partially compensated for by increased von Willebrand factor. Disturbances in secondary hemostasis include reduced synthesis of coagulation factors, as well as concurrent decreased synthesis of anticoagulants: Protein C, Protein S, and Antithrombin. Many patients with cirrhosis are in a state of hyperfibrinolysis (increased tPA), causing clinically significant bleeding due to rapid clot breakdown; reduced fibrinogen levels worsen clot quality (González-González et al. 2011; Islam et al. 2022).

On the other hand, septic states and hepatocyte necrosis lead to systemic activation of coagulation (via tissue factor release). The liver cannot clear activated factors, resulting in microvascular thrombosis and organ dysfunction. Depletion of platelets and hyperfibrinolysis eventually lead to severe bleeding—essentially the development of DIC syndrome (Islam et al. 2022).

Treatment discussion

Depending on the source of bleeding—variceal, ulcerative, or diffuse—appropriate treatment must be applied according to established guidelines. Urgent endoscopy is performed within 6 hours of hospitalization. First-line treatment is variceal band ligation. Absolute contraindications for performing the procedure are shock and coma. Balloon tamponade (inserting a Blakemore–Sengstaken tube) is a second-line option, as it has many risk fac-

tors—aspiration pneumonia, tissue necrosis, and others. If bleeding persists after two endoscopies or balloon tamponade, TIPS (transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt) may be placed.

The primary prophylaxis of a variceal bleed lies in the treatment of portal hypertension and reduction of portal pressure. Treatment with non-selective beta-blockers, mainly propranolol (or nadolol), is started at 10–12.5 mg and titrated every 3–5 days to approximately 2×20 mg/day. The aim is to reduce the heart rate by 25% but not below 55 bpm. Abrupt discontinuation may cause rebound hypertension and bleeding. Terlipressin is a vasopressin analogue that causes splanchnic vasoconstriction and preserves renal function. Somatostatin decreases portal blood flow, while potassium-preserving diuretics such as spironolactone decrease portal pressure through intrahepatic vasodilation and aldosterone antagonism (Gralnek et al. 2022).

In patients with a non-variceal source of bleeding, a hemodynamic assessment is performed first. In all cases of acute upper GI bleeding, cardiac function and blood pressure should be evaluated immediately. In cases of hemodynamic instability, rapid resuscitation with crystalloid solutions should be initiated (strong recommendation). Risk stratification before endoscopy—The Glasgow-Blatchford Score (GBS) is used for preliminary assessment. Patients with GBS 0–1 are considered very low risk and may be discharged without the need for urgent endoscopy or hospitalization; they should then be informed about the risk of rebleeding (Hearnshaw et al. 2011; Sanders et al. 2011).

The haemotransfusion strategy aims to maintain an acceptable hemoglobin range of 7–9 g/dL. In patients with significant comorbidities (e.g., ischemic heart disease), a higher target may be selected. Intravenous proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) are recommended before endoscopy; a high dose of PPI should be administered (80 mg bolus, followed by an 8 mg/h infusion). The infusion should not delay endoscopy. After stabilization, endoscopy should be performed within 24 hours. In high-risk situations (persistent hypotension/tachycardia, active bleeding, contraindications to stopping anticoagulants), it may be performed within 12 hours.

Cases with an active bleeding ulcer (Forrest Ia, Ib) and ulcers with a visible vessel (Forrest IIa) should be treated endoscopically. In ulcers with an adherent clot (Forrest IIb), the clot should be removed; hemostasis is then applied if active bleeding or a visible vessel is identified. In ulcers with a flat pigmented spot (Forrest IIc) or a clean base (Forrest III), endoscopic hemostasis is not required; patients may be discharged with oral PPI therapy. Epinephrine injection should not be used as a single method; it must always be combined with a second endoscopic technique. After successful hemostasis, high-dose PPI should be continued (80 mg bolus, 8 mg/h for 72 hours). A second endoscopy is not recommended routinely but should be performed if there are clinical signs of rebleeding; if unsuccessful, trans-arterial embolization or surgery should be pursued.

It must not be forgotten that managing coagulation disorders is crucial for both the duration of hospitalization and the overall prognosis of the patient (Hearnshaw et al. 2011; Sanders et al. 2011). Treatment of coagulopathy should be based on individualized assessment, not routine correction. Targeted replacement of identified deficiencies should be applied: fresh frozen plasma or coagulation factor concentrates when a specific factor deficiency is present; in low fibrinogen (< 1.5–2.0 g/L), fibrinogen concentrate or cryoprecipitate should be given; thrombocytopenia (< 50 × 10⁹/L) with active bleeding requires platelet transfusion; in a state of hyperfibrinolysis, antifibrinolytics (tranexamic acid) should be applied. Thromboprophylaxis should not be overlooked—low molecular weight heparin may be safely administered in selected patients with preserved portal flow (Islam et al. 2022).

Conclusion

Our conclusions, based on the 3 years of data, show the following: One should not assume that a cirrhotic patient with GI bleeding has a variceal source; a considerable proportion have non-variceal causes. Patients present at all times of the day, requiring medical teams to be prepared to initiate diagnostic and therapeutic measures at any moment. Managing coagulopathy is a key component of the overall treatment of such patients. First, an assessment of the patient's hemodynamic status is performed. Endoscopic treatment is carried out based on the source of bleeding. Considering the studied group of patients, inclusion of prophylactic therapy with medications that reduce pressure in the portal system is required. If an ulcer etiology of the bleeding is identified, treatment with a proton pump inhibitor should also be initiated. PPI therapy improves the stability of the blood clot in patients with pronounced coagulopathy.

Our study showed that in about 26.3% of the cirrhotic patients with upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage, the bleeding occurred from non-variceal sources, of which the most frequent one was ulcer. The large number of non-variceal bleeding cases in cirrhotic patients shows the importance of upper gastrointestinal endoscopy for specifying the etiology of upper gastrointestinal bleeding and for establishing the appropriate therapy.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

Clinical trials: Ek-07-25/15.12.25.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Multidisciplinary Hospital for Active Treatment and Emergency Medicine "N. I. Pirogov".

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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